

Title

Applying Modular Design Principles of Adverse Outcome Pathways to Experimental Planning in Toxicology

Author

D. A. Barnes¹, F. A. Redegeld¹, R. Masereeuw¹

ORCID*s*

1. D. A. Barnes (0000-0003-2037-2824)
2. F. A. Redegeld (0000-0001-8830-7960)
3. R. Masereeuw (0000-0002-1560-1074)

Affiliations

¹Utrecht University, Division of Pharmacology, Utrecht Institute for Pharmaceutical Sciences, Utrecht, Netherlands

Abstract

Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) offer a modular framework that can transform experimental planning in toxicology beyond their current use in organising knowledge. This commentary highlights how adopting modular AOP principles, treating each experimental design element as an interconnected module, can bridge mechanistic understanding, improve data integration, and pave the way for more efficient, mechanism-based toxicity testing. The systematic application of these principles not only streamlines resource use and supports non-animal methods but also enhances the predictive and regulatory relevance of toxicological studies. Viewed this way, modular experimental planning complements AOP-informed Defined Approaches (DA) and Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) by improving how evidence-generating modules are designed, reported, and integrated; it is most immediately actionable in mechanistic research and NAM development that support regulatory decision-making.

Keywords

Adverse outcome pathway, modular design, experimental planning, toxicology

Current Challenges in Toxicological Experimental Design

Experimental design in toxicology continues to struggle with capturing the mechanistic complexity of toxic responses. Conventional, guideline-driven toxicity testing frameworks, often centred on animal studies with apical endpoints, built around standardised, prescriptive protocols have ensured reproducibility and regulatory compliance but often prioritise consistency and statistical robustness over mechanistic insight (1). These designs typically emphasise pre-specified apical endpoints collected at predetermined timepoints rather than elucidating how molecular and cellular perturbations lead to organism-level outcomes. The result is a reproducible evidence base that can establish causality between exposure and apical adverse outcomes, but often offers limited resolution on the mechanistic causal chain (i.e., which molecular/cellular events drive the observed outcome). This compartmentalised approach originates from a hazard-identification paradigm that values comparability across laboratories and chemicals over mechanistic exploration. In guideline-driven regulatory testing, model systems and core endpoints are largely dictated by legislated requirements and standardised test guidelines. As a result, mechanistic frameworks such as AOPs are often incorporated mainly in weight-of-evidence interpretation and targeted follow-up studies, rather than explicitly structuring primary study design (2, 3). While this uniformity supports regulatory goals, it restricts flexibility and hinders the integration of emerging biological knowledge.

Standardised protocols remain essential for regulatory acceptance and cross-study comparability, but their rigidity can be counterproductive. Many guidelines prescribe dose ranges, exposure durations, and endpoints a priori, even when ill-suited to the biology of interest, confirming toxicity yet failing to explain why it occurs (4). A related misalignment can also occur in academic toxicology, where study components are selected without explicit anchoring to a mechanistic framework. This misalignment between prescribed designs and mechanistic evidence wastes resources, complicates dataset integration, and limits the predictive value of results for modelling and read-across. These challenges are increasingly apparent as toxicology shifts toward new approach methodologies (NAMs), used here to refer broadly to non-animal *in vitro*, *in chemico*, *in silico*, and other mechanistically informative methods and testing strategies, and toward more integrated, standardised approaches to evidence generation (5). The field is moving from descriptive, animal-based hazard identification to predictive, mechanism-oriented frameworks that link key biological events across levels of organisation (6). These approaches depend on clear mechanistic hypotheses, cross-scale data integration, and iterative model refinement. Yet to fully realise the potential of NAMs, mechanistically informative methods need to be embedded in experimental designs that explicitly align assay selection, exposure conditions, timing, and interpretation with the mechanistic pathway or key events (KEs) under study.

To enable this transition, toxicology needs a new experimental philosophy that treats study components as adaptable, interconnected modules for probing specific toxicity pathways. Applying modular design principles, akin to those underpinning AOP development, can make experimental planning more explicit, traceable, and hypothesis-led, particularly in research and NAM development, while improving how evidence is assembled for regulatory application. This shift would help bridge mechanistic understanding and regulatory application, enhancing the efficiency, interpretability, and predictive power of toxicological testing. This commentary examines how modular planning can strengthen mechanistic toxicology research and support the development of AOP-informed testing strategies, often involving NAMs and integrated evidence streams, that may ultimately inform regulatory decision-making. We use “traditional testing” to refer to conventional, guideline-driven hazard identification approaches, most commonly animal-based *in vivo* studies with apical endpoints, along with other prescriptive protocols designed for comparability rather than pathway-level hypothesis testing. We also acknowledge that routine regulatory guideline studies often allow limited

flexibility; accordingly, modular planning is most immediately actionable upstream (method development, prioritisation, targeted follow-up studies) and, where permitted, through mechanistically motivated choices within guideline constraints (e.g., selecting timepoints and endpoints, and anchoring interpretation to an AOP segment).

AOP-informed Defined Approaches (DAs) and Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) are established frameworks for structuring mechanistically informed testing and assessment strategies, including the selection, combination, and interpretation of assays and other evidence streams for hazard or risk decisions. The modular approach proposed here is complementary but distinct, providing a study-design lens for planning, specifying, and documenting the experimental modules that can contribute to such strategies. Specifically, it emphasises (i) traceability, by mapping each module to a KE/KER question; (ii) interoperability, by specifying module inputs/outputs and metadata to enable integration with computational toxicology and PBK/PBPK models; and (iii) reusability, by allowing modules to be swapped and recombined as AOP evidence evolves. Modular planning can further help bridge research outputs to regulatory use by generating and reporting data in more assessment-ready formats, making module-level assumptions, quality criteria, and metadata explicit, consistent with recent OECD guidance on the lifecycle of research data for regulatory assessments (7).

Foundations of Modular Design in AOPs

In this context, modular design means breaking a complex toxicology question into a small set of interoperable components (“modules”) with defined purpose, inputs, and outputs. In practice, a module may be (i) a specific assay configured to measure a KE/KER-relevant biological change, (ii) an exposure regimen chosen to probe time-dependent dynamics, (iii) an endpoint set that operationalises a mechanistic hypothesis, or (iv) an analysis step that links measurements across levels of biology. The key is that modules are specified so they can be reused, swapped, and recombined without redesigning the entire study, provided their objectives and readouts are clearly defined.

The Modular Logic of Adverse Outcome Pathways

Modular design principles are a staple of adverse outcome pathway (AOP) development, offering untapped potential to enhance experimental planning in toxicological research. AOPs have emerged as valuable frameworks for organising scientific knowledge of toxicological processes. They describe a sequential chain of causally linked events from an initial interaction with a stressor, dubbed the molecular initiating event (MIE), through intermediate, well-defined KEs via key event relationships (KERs) to an adverse outcome (AO) at the organism or population level (8, 9). Each KE represents a measurable biological state or process, while each KER defines how one event influences another. Because these elements are modular, they can be reused across multiple pathways and refined as new data emerge. The modular structure of AOPs has been instrumental in making complex toxicological processes more accessible and actionable for hazard identification and mechanism-based risk prioritisation (10). The utility of modularity becomes even more apparent within AOP networks, where shared KEs link diverse pathways. For example, oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction and cell death are recurrent modules across multiple toxicity domains, including hepatotoxicity, neurotoxicity, and nephrotoxicity (11-13). This reusability fosters consistency, reduces duplication of effort, and supports the accumulation of evidence. Building on this logic, we propose applying modularity directly to experimental planning. Each experimental module should be explicitly mapped to the KE or KER it is intended to test, and a study (or testing strategy) can be viewed as the assembly of modules chosen to reduce uncertainty in the AOP segment most relevant to the decision at hand. Put simply, the AOP

is the mechanistic map, and the modules are the measurements used to interrogate defined parts of that map.

Such a modular approach allows toxicologists to integrate diverse data sources, conduct targeted investigations, and build upon existing knowledge in a systematic manner (14, 15). However, while modularity has been embraced in organising toxicological knowledge, such as within systems biology strategies (16) and quantitative AOP (qAOP) development (17), its systemic application to experimental design remains unevenly operationalised across domains, despite clear momentum in several 'next-generation' initiatives. Examples include AOP-informed DAs for skin sensitisation (3, 18) and emerging AOP-anchored in vitro batteries in domains such as developmental neurotoxicity (19). Translating the modular logic of AOPs into how experiments are conceived and executed offers a powerful opportunity to bridge experimental and computational toxicology. Toxicologists and study designers could generate more mechanistically informative and efficient testing strategies that better align with regulatory needs by explicitly mapping each design module to an AOP KE/KER question and documenting module inputs/outputs, quality criteria, and uncertainties in a form that supports evidence evaluation and integration. Recent OECD guidance on the generation, reporting and use of research data for regulatory assessments emphasises lifecycle-aware documentation (generation, reporting, identification, evaluation and integration) and highlights practical actions to improve the reliability, relevance, and uptake of research outputs (7). In this conceptual framework, AOPs provide a map of biological causality, while experimental design involves strategically selecting and linking modules to probe specific causal relationships. Aligning each element of a study—model system, compound, exposure, and assay, with corresponding KEs or KERs can make experimentation more systematic, hypothesis-driven, and mechanistically informative.

AOP-informed testing strategies are already being implemented in OECD-aligned and regulatory-facing initiatives, including DAs for skin sensitisation (e.g., OECD TG 497) (18), emerging toxicogenomic information sources under OECD consultation (e.g., draft SENS-IS) (20), and AOP-informed case studies such as the EFSA tebufenpyrad NAM pilot (21). The contribution of this commentary is not to suggest that AOP-guided assay selection is absent, but to generalise and make explicit a modular experimental planning layer that extends beyond KE coverage: (i) module specification (objective/KE–KER link, defined inputs/outputs, controls and acceptance criteria, metadata), (ii) inclusion of non-assay modules such as exposure design, dosimetry/PBK–IVIVE anchoring, and a pre-specified evidence integration/interpretation plan, and (iii) iterative updating of strategies as AOP evidence evolves.

Applying Modular Thinking to Experimental Design

The elements below are presented as design modules, not a rigid stepwise checklist. Depending on the question and context, modules can be used individually (to improve a single experiment) or combined iteratively (to build a testing strategy).

Implementation guide: a modular AOP-informed planning workflow.

1. **Define the decision context** (screening, prioritisation, mechanistic research, or regulatory support) and the relevant biological domain.
2. **Select the AOP (or AOP network) segment** that is most decision-relevant (which KEs/KERs matter for the conclusion).
3. **Translate the AOP segment into testable questions** and list key uncertainties (plausibility, dose–response, temporal order, essentiality, applicability domain).
4. **Assemble the study from modules** (biological system + assays, exposure design/dosimetry, analysis, and interpretation), explicitly mapping each module to a KE or KER question.
5. **Pre-specify integration and iteration rules:** how module outputs will be interpreted, how uncertainty will be handled, and which additional/swapped modules would be used if evidence is insufficient.

Figure 1 summarises a minimal module specification checklist to support reproducible reporting, reuse, and integration across modules.

Figure 1. Minimal module specification workflow for AOP-informed experimental planning. Flowchart summarising the core information to document for each experimental module linked to a Key Event (KE) or Key Event Relationship (KER). The workflow begins by defining the objective and KE/KER link, followed by selection of the biological system. Exposure design (dose and timing) and readouts/endpoints (including units and timepoints) are specified alongside controls and acceptance criteria. A pre-specified analysis plan supports transparent interpretation, and output format and metadata are recorded to enable integration, reuse, and interoperability across modules and testing strategies.

Formulating hypotheses with modular AOP logic

Modular planning is most useful when it begins with an explicit hypothesis that is traceable to an AOP segment and testable with a defined set of modules. In practice, hypothesis formulation can start from different knowledge states; the modular approach provides a consistent way to translate each starting point into testable KE/KER questions, and then into modules (biological system + assays, exposure regimen, and interpretation plan).

Starting point 1: Known or suspected MIE

If a plausible MIE is known (e.g., receptor binding, enzyme inhibition), the primary hypothesis can be framed as: “Chemical X triggers MIE Y at biologically relevant exposure, leading to a predictable progression of downstream KEs consistent with the AOP.” Modules are selected to (i) test the MIE with specificity, (ii) confirm temporal and dose–response concordance across one or more downstream KEs, and (iii) evaluate biological domain relevance (metabolism competence, target cell types).

Starting point 2: Apical observation/AO-first (reverse engineering)

If an AO/apical observation is known but the mechanism is uncertain, hypothesis formulation proceeds by selecting the most plausible AOP(s) or AOP network(s) consistent with the phenotype, then posing competing hypotheses: “AO Z arises via pathway A (KE set 1) versus pathway B (KE set 2).” Modules are chosen to discriminate between pathways by targeting early KEs with high diagnostic value, followed by confirmatory downstream KEs if needed.

Starting point 3: Unknown MoA (exploratory probing)

When neither MIE nor AOP assignment is clear, modular planning supports an exploratory hypothesis framed around KE patterns rather than a single initiating event: “Chemical X perturbs one of several candidate stress-response/toxicity pathways, which can be detected as a characteristic KE signature over time.” Modules are selected as a small, diverse panel covering candidate KE families (e.g., oxidative stress, inflammation, cytotoxicity, endocrine disruption), coupled with time-resolved exposure design; results then refine the working AOP hypothesis and guide a second iteration with more specific modules.

Worked example (illustrative, AO-first → hypothesis → modules).

Modular hypotheses can start from a known/suspected MIE (forward testing), an AO/apical observation (reverse engineering), or an uncertain MoA (exploratory KE probing). An illustrative kidney-toxicity worked example is summarised in Figure 2. The figure shows how an AO-first starting point can be translated into three competing mechanistic hypotheses and corresponding KE-relevant modules (kidney epithelial, glomerular, and immune/stress), supported by time-resolved exposure and PBK/IVIVE modules. Evidence is then integrated using pre-defined rules (directionality, temporal order, concordance, and uncertainty appraisal) to discriminate between hypotheses and identify follow-up modules if needed.

Figure 2. Worked kidney-toxicity example illustrating modular, AOP-informed hypothesis testing and evidence integration. An apical kidney-toxicity signal is used to formulate three competing mechanistic hypotheses (top row). Each hypothesis is translated into KE-relevant experimental modules (middle row), here illustrated as kidney epithelial (proximal tubule), glomerular, and immune/stress modules. These are supported by a time-resolved exposure module and PBK/IVIVE module (lower middle) to align exposure timing and concentration/dosimetry assumptions. Outputs are integrated using pre-defined rules (bottom) that consider directionality, temporal order, concordance, and uncertainty appraisal to discriminate between hypotheses and guide iterative follow-up module selection. (*KE: key event; PBK: physiologically based kinetic; IVIVE: in vitro-to-in vivo extrapolation.*)

Design Modules

Biological system and assay module selection (KE/KER mapping)

Biological system and assay modules should be selected together so each module is fit for purpose for the KE/KER question. Begin by defining the biological domain, such as species/taxon, sex or life stage where relevant, tissue or cell type, and key competencies such as metabolic capacity or immune crosstalk. Translate the KE/KER questions into system requirements (e.g., target cell type(s), necessary receptor/enzyme machinery, differentiation state, tissue architecture), then choose assays and readouts that operationalise the KE/KER with appropriate specificity, dynamic range, and time resolution. Ensure that the controls and acceptance criteria are defined up front.

Modular design does not require a single system to capture an entire pathway. Use one system when it credibly covers the AOP segment relevant to the decision; use parallel, KE-level modules when events span biological scales or require distinct contexts (e.g., metabolism-dependent toxicity, epithelial-immune interactions, tissue remodelling). Ensure modules connect through defined interfaces—

harmonised exposure metrics, aligned sampling times, and shared controls or reference chemicals—and specify how evidence will be integrated. To support reuse, characterise each system’s context by reporting baseline identity and function (pathway competence, relevant marker expression), limitations, and quality criteria. Where available, omics profiling can strengthen context annotation and improve cross-system comparability.

Stressor/chemical selection and applicability domain

Stressor selection is most relevant in mechanism-focused research, method development, prioritisation, read-across, and mixture assessment, where representative compounds or comparators help probe pathway logic and define an assay’s applicability domain. In regulatory assessment of a specific substance, the primary chemical is predefined; however, this module still supports selection of reference chemicals, structurally related analogues, and positive/negative controls to test key uncertainties (specificity, potency ranking, expected KE progression).

Exposure design and dosimetry module

Treat exposure as a first-class module. Choose acute vs repeated regimens and sampling timepoints to match expected KE dynamics and KER directionality. Where possible, incorporate dosimetry and PBK/PBPK/IVIVE to relate nominal concentrations to internal exposure metrics and to support cross-system integration.

Molecular annotation and omics-enabled KE modules.

Molecular annotation of AOP KEs (linking KEs to genes, proteins, and pathways) enables modules to be reusable and computationally interoperable (14). Omics readouts can serve as high-content KE modules: they can strengthen targeted assays by providing pathway-level context and supporting hypothesis refinement, and in some cases reduce reliance on large panels of targeted assays for early/molecular KEs, provided signatures are sufficiently anchored and interpretation rules are pre-specified. To maximise reuse and regulatory usability, omics modules should be reported with transparent processing and metadata using harmonised reporting recommendations (e.g., the OECD Omics Reporting Framework) (22).

Evidence integration and interpretation plan (pre-specified)

Treat interpretation as a module. Define what constitutes support for a KE/KER (directionality, temporal concordance, dose–response consistency), how uncertainty will be evaluated (assay limitations, biological domain relevance, confounding, reproducibility), and how evidence will be integrated (weight-of-evidence narrative, quantitative models, or anchored points of departure). Pre-specifying interpretation reduces post hoc rationalisation and increases comparability and regulatory usability.

Benefits of a Modular Approach to Experimental Design

Modular thinking offers both practical and conceptual advantages for experimental toxicology. Analogous modular formats have already been formalised in other fields, such as intensified design-of-experiments (DoE) approaches including the one-factor-multiple-columns (OFMC) format, illustrating how reusable experimental “building blocks” can improve efficiency and interpretability (23). This approach describes stage-dependent factor effects and potential memory effects during a bioprocess, to better determine which factor settings are most beneficial at different stages of mammalian cell culture. The OFMC format demonstrates how modular thinking can simplify planning, facilitate data acquisition, ease modelling, and provide a straightforward quantification of complex

biological responses by explicitly linking each variable to a defined stage of the process. Applying similar logic to toxicological experimentation could yield comparable benefits, particularly in capturing the stage-dependent effects of chemical exposures and cellular adaptations over time.

A further advantage of modular planning is that it can generate AOP-aligned evidence in formats readily interoperable with DA/IATA workflows. For example, consider a regulatory prioritisation question for a predefined chemical X suspected to perturb a liver injury-to-fibrosis pathway segment. A modular strategy would begin by selecting the relevant AOP segment and translating it into uncertainties to be reduced (e.g., plausibility, temporal concordance, dose-response, and biological domain relevance). The study can then be assembled from interoperable modules: (i) KE-mapped biological system and assay modules (e.g., hepatocyte stress/injury readouts; inflammatory signalling; stellate cell activation; matrix deposition in a more complex co-culture), each with defined controls and acceptance criteria; (ii) an exposure module (e.g., repeated low-dose regimens with time-series sampling) matched to expected KE dynamics; (iii) a dosimetry/PBK-IVIVE module to relate *in vitro* effective concentrations to plausible internal exposure; and (iv) a pre-specified integration/interpretation module that defines how evidence will be combined (directionality, temporal order, concordance) and how uncertainty will be handled. If gaps remain, modules can be swapped or added (e.g., metabolism-competent systems, additional KE assays) without redesigning the entire strategy, emphasising how evidence-generating components are designed and reported so they remain mechanistically traceable and interoperable within IATA and, where appropriate, future DAs.

Adopting a modular approach to experimental design provides numerous benefits that enhance the quality and applicability of scientific research. Experiments designed with AOP modules in mind are more likely to generate mechanistically interpretable data that can help to inform and improve risk assessment processes. As demonstrated by the OFMC-inspired framework and targeted assay selection examples, modular planning enables the coherent integration of results from discrete components across time and biological levels. For instance, modular alignment of *in vitro* assays to AOP-defined KEs, as shown in the EFSA tebufenpyrad project (21), illustrates how targeted design can replace broad, resource-intensive test batteries while maintaining mechanistic fidelity. This approach also promotes better integration with existing knowledge by aligning experimental designs with established KEs and KERs, enabling new data to complement prior findings seamlessly (13, 24). Furthermore, modular designs optimise resource utilisation by targeting specific knowledge gaps in toxicity pathways rather than adhering to rigid standardised protocols (25). This efficiency supports the advancement of non-animal methods, as modular frameworks establish clear connections among *in vitro*, *in silico*, and *in vivo* approaches. Beyond efficiency, modular experimental planning can strengthen rigour and reproducibility by making module objectives, inputs/outputs, controls, and analysis assumptions explicit, and it can improve the regulatory usability of research outputs by aligning reporting and metadata with emerging expectations for transparent, lifecycle-aware research data intended for regulatory assessment (7), including omics-based modules (22).

Ultimately, modular experimental design fosters a natural synergy with computational modelling. Data generated through modular experiments are structured and mechanistically annotated, making them well-suited for integration into quantitative AOPs, Bayesian networks, and machine learning approaches (17, 26). These computational tools, in turn, can identify where new modules are needed, creating an iterative feedback loop between experimentation and prediction. Together, these benefits transform toxicological research from a static, endpoint-driven enterprise into a dynamic, integrative, and predictive discipline in which each experiment contributes meaningfully to a growing, interconnected understanding of the mechanisms of toxicity.

Conclusion and Future Directions

This commentary offers a conceptual and practical planning lens rather than a full operational framework. We do not propose new regulatory decision rules, replace DA/IATA guidance, or provide exhaustive case studies for specific endpoints or sectors. Instead, we aim to clarify how AOP modularity can be mirrored in experimental design and to sketch compact templates that can be expanded in future work. The modular design principles that have enhanced our ability to organise toxicological knowledge through AOPs can and should be applied to experimental planning.

By treating experimental elements as interoperable modules, researchers involved in planning toxicological studies, including academic scientists, method developers, and regulatory or industrial scientists, can create more informative, efficient, and mechanistically relevant studies by conceptualising experimental design elements as modules that connect to specific aspects of toxicity pathways. This approach can strengthen the reproducibility and interpretability of toxicological research, improve integration across data streams, and help align experimental design with both mechanistic insight and regulatory applicability, contributing to more transparent and scientifically robust risk assessment. As toxicology evolves toward more mechanistic, predictive approaches, aligning experimental design with modular toxicity pathways will become increasingly important, and will support the ongoing transition toward NAMs and predictive toxicology.

Future work should focus on developing formalised frameworks and tools to guide the application of modular thinking in experimental planning, ultimately enhancing our ability to assess chemical safety while reducing reliance on animal testing. Efforts to operationalise modular experimental design through standardised templates, curated module libraries, and community-developed best practice guidelines could enable broader adoption and more consistent implementation. Collaborative efforts between academia and regulators could establish harmonised practices for modular experimental planning. As AOP-informed methods continue to evolve, a modular approach to experimental design offers a clear pathway to integrate emerging technologies, such as high-content omics and computational models, into coherent, hypothesis-driven toxicity testing strategies. In doing so, toxicology can move beyond rigid, endpoint-driven testing toward a future in which experimental design is a dynamic, mechanistically integrated process that strengthens the scientific foundation of risk assessment while advancing the replacement, reduction, and refinement of animal use. By making design decisions explicit, reusable, and easier to pre-specify and appraise, modular experimental planning can also strengthen downstream evidence synthesis and decision transparency.

CRedit statement

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Conflict of interest

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References

1. Bas A, Burns N, Gulotta A, Junker J, Drasler B, Lehner R, et al. Understanding the Development, Standardization, and Validation Process of Alternative In Vitro Test Methods for Regulatory Approval from a Researcher Perspective. *Small*. 2021;17(15):e2006027.
2. Manservigi F, Marquillas CB, Buscaroli A, Huff J, Lauriola M, Mandrioli D, et al. An Integrated Experimental Design for the Assessment of Multiple Toxicological End Points in Rat Bioassays. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2017;125(3):289-95.
3. Jaworska J, Harol A, Kern PS, Gerberick GF. Integrating non-animal test information into an adaptive testing strategy - skin sensitization proof of concept case. *ALTEX*. 2011;28(3):211-25.
4. Hartung T. A toxicology for the 21st century--mapping the road ahead. *Toxicol Sci*. 2009;109(1):18-23.
5. Network EUI. New Approach Methodologies: EU-IN Horizon Scanning Report. European Medicines Agency; 2025 2025/02. Contract No.: EMA/56850/2025.
6. Sewell F, Alexander-White C, Brescia S, Currie RA, Roberts R, Roper C, et al. New approach methodologies (NAMs): identifying and overcoming hurdles to accelerated adoption. *Toxicol Res (Camb)*. 2024;13(2):tfae044.
7. OECD. Guidance Document on the Generation, Reporting and Use of Research Data for Regulatory Assessments. Paris; 2025.
8. Ankley GT, Bennett RS, Erickson RJ, Hoff DJ, Hornung MW, Johnson RD, et al. Adverse outcome pathways: A conceptual framework to support ecotoxicology research and risk assessment. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*. 2010;29(3):730-41.
9. Vinken M. The adverse outcome pathway concept: a pragmatic tool in toxicology. *Toxicology*. 2013;312:158-65.
10. Bajard L, Adamovsky O, Audouze K, Baken K, Barouki R, Beltman JB, et al. Application of AOPs to assist regulatory assessment of chemical risks - Case studies, needs and recommendations. *Environ Res*. 2023;217:114650.
11. Arnesdotter E, Spinu N, Firman J, Ebbrell D, Cronin MTD, Vanhaecke T, et al. Derivation, characterisation and analysis of an adverse outcome pathway network for human hepatotoxicity. *Toxicology*. 2021;459:152856.
12. Spinu N, Bal-Price A, Cronin MTD, Enoch SJ, Madden JC, Worth AP. Development and analysis of an adverse outcome pathway network for human neurotoxicity. *Arch Toxicol*. 2019;93(10):2759-72.
13. Barnes DA, Firman JW, Belfield SJ, Cronin MTD, Vinken M, Janssen MJ, et al. Development of an adverse outcome pathway network for nephrotoxicity. *Arch Toxicol*. 2024;98(3):929-42.
14. Saarimaki LA, Fratello M, Pavel A, Korpilahde S, Leppanen J, Serra A, et al. A curated gene and biological system annotation of adverse outcome pathways related to human health. *Sci Data*. 2023;10(1):409.
15. Svingen T, Villeneuve DL, Knapen D, Panagiotou EM, Draskau MK, Damdimopoulou P, et al. A Pragmatic Approach to Adverse Outcome Pathway Development and Evaluation. *Toxicol Sci*. 2021;184(2):183-90.
16. Jaylet T, Quintens R, Armant O, Audouze K. An integrative systems biology strategy to support the development of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs): a case study on radiation-induced microcephaly. *Front Cell Dev Biol*. 2023;11:1197204.
17. Foran CM, Rycroft T, Keisler J, Perkins EJ, Linkov I, Garcia-Reyero N. A modular approach for assembly of quantitative adverse outcome pathways. *ALTEX*. 2019;36(3):353-62.
18. OECD. Guideline No. 497: Defined Approaches on Skin Sensitisation. Paris; 2025.
19. European Food Safety A, Crofton KM, Paparella M, Price A, Mangas I, Martino L, et al. A developmental neurotoxicity adverse outcome pathway (DNT-AOP) with voltage gate sodium channel (VGSC) inhibition as a molecular initiating event (MiE). *EFSA J*. 2024;22(8):e8954.

20. OECD. Draft New Test Guideline of the SENS-IS. 2025.
21. Alimohammadi M, Meyburg B, Ückert A-K, Holzer A-K, Leist M. EFSA Pilot Project on New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for Tebufenpyrad Risk Assessment. Part 2. Hazard characterisation and identification of the Reference Point. EFSA Supporting Publications. 2023.
22. OECD. OECD Omics Reporting Framework (OORF): Guidance on reporting elements for the regulatory use of omics data from laboratory-based toxicology studies. Paris; 2023. Contract No.: 390.
23. Kienzle S, Junghans L, Wieschalka S, Diem K, Takors R, Radde NE, et al. Direct Consideration of Process History During Intensified Design of Experiments Planning Eases Interpretation of Mammalian Cell Culture Dynamics. *Bioengineering (Basel)*. 2025;12(3).
24. Sanz-Serrano J, Callewaert E, De Boever S, Drees A, Verhoeven A, Vinken M. Chemical-induced liver cancer: an adverse outcome pathway perspective. *Expert Opin Drug Saf*. 2024;23(4):425-38.
25. Wiklund L, Caccia S, Pipal M, Nymark P, Beronius A. Development of a data-driven approach to Adverse Outcome Pathway network generation: a case study on the EATS-modalities. *Front Toxicol*. 2023;5:1183824.
26. Ito S, Mukherjee S, Erami K, Muratani S, Mori A, Ichikawa S, et al. Proof of concept for quantitative adverse outcome pathway modeling of chronic toxicity in repeated exposure. *Sci Rep*. 2024;14(1):4741.